

A Comparative Analysis of ESG Initiatives and Corporate Performance in the Philippine Oil Industry Using Power BI

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ABSTRACT

The oil and natural gas industries are vital to both the global and Philippine economies, providing essential energy sources. The Philippine oil sector is highly competitive, with oil demand projected to grow 3.4% annually from 2022 to 2031 (Neil, 2023). Petron and Shell are among the "Big Three" in the industry, with market shares of 23.19% and 15.55%, respectively. This study compares the 2023 sustainability initiatives of Shell Pilipinas Corporation (SPC) and Petron Corporation, focusing on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices and their potential link to corporate performance. Using a comparative analysis design, the study evaluated ESG indicators and visualized data from each company's 2023 sustainability and financial reports. Findings reveal that Shell leads environmentally with a net-zero target by 2050 and more solar-powered sites, while Petron is improving emissions but lacks a specific net-zero goal. Socially, Shell recorded higher community investments. In terms of governance, both adhere to reporting standards, but Shell aligns with more international frameworks. Financially, Petron showed stronger net income and earnings growth in 2023. The study recommends further ESG integration across the industry. The results support the idea that ESG initiatives contribute to operational efficiency and long-term profitability in the Philippine oil sector.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study / Objective

The oil and natural gas industries are critical to both the global and Philippine economies, providing essential energy sources (Department of Energy, 2022). The Philippines relies heavily on indigenous conventional fuels, including petroleum products, with finished petroleum products reaching 2,195 ML by the end of 2023 (DOE, 2023). Shell Pilipinas Corporation (SPC), a major player in this sector, imports and markets products like gasoline, diesel, jet fuel, fuel

oil, lubricants, and bitumen (SPC, 2023). Another key player to the Philippines' oil industry is Petron Corporation, supplying around 40% of the country's total fuel requirement (*Who We Are - Petron*, 2024).

In today's global business landscape, investing in the sustainable-power value chain can provide an opportunity to diversify and play a leading role as the industry transitions (Kienzler et al., 2023). As a result, growing demand to embrace sustainable practices that address environmental, social, and governance (ESG) concerns arises (Ogunbukola, 2024). That said, both companies have presented their mission towards sustainability as the traditional business model of oil and gas is under pressure.

The Philippine oil industry is highly competitive, with oil demand expected to grow 3.4% annually from 2022 to 2031 (Neil, 2023). The "Big Three" — Petron, Shell, and Chevron — control 42% of the market, with Petron leading at 23.19%, Shell at 15.55%, and Chevron at 4.40% (Statista, 2024; Philstar, 2022). Shell faces intense competition and is influenced by factors like government policies, oil prices, and environmental regulations (The Strategy Story, 2023). The company has been consistent with their sustainability efforts through annual reports in recent years (Shell Pilipinas, 2024). On the other hand, Petron Corporation, the leading top oil company in the country, has reported their process of setting targets to integrate climate action strategies into their operations (Petron Corporation, 2024). This study compares and examines the sustainability initiatives of Shell Pilipinas Corporation (SPC) and Petron Corporation in 2023.

Relative to this, research shows that top Morgan Stanley Capital International (MSCI) ESG-rated companies have consistently outperformed their lower-rated peers due chiefly to better earnings fundamentals (Eling-Lee, 2024). Analyzing Shell Pilipinas' and Petron's sustainability initiatives, in accordance with the environmental, social, and governance (ESG)

concerns, helps explain the companies' corporate performance.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sustainability has become an important part of the oil and gas industry around the world. Okeke (2021) conducted a content analysis of annual reports from fifteen leading oil and gas companies across Europe, America, and Asia to identify where these companies placed their emphasis regarding sustainability, where it was found that many oil companies are focusing on reducing their environmental impact. This shift is part of a global trend where companies are expected to care not only about profits but also about the environment and society. Li (2024) supports this idea by showing how Shell includes sustainability in its overall business strategy to stay competitive and responsible.

In the Philippines, leading oil companies like Petron and Shell are also making efforts toward sustainability. Enverga (2023) explains that Petron is working to protect the environment by improving its operations and introducing new environmental programs. Shell, on the other hand, focuses on lowering carbon emissions throughout the life cycle of its products, from production to end use (King, 2023).

The importance of sustainability is not only about helping the environment it also affects how well a company performs in the long run. Lee (2024) reports that companies with strong environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices often do better financially. A report by the Center on Global Energy Policy (Palacios & Vidotto Caricati, 2023) also highlights how national oil companies are being rated based on their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) efforts, helping investors and the public see how serious these companies are about sustainability.

In the Philippine context, the International Trade Administration (2021) gives an overview of the oil and gas industry, including opportunities and challenges for local and foreign investors. This helps provide a background for understanding how companies like Shell and Petron operate in the country.

Overall, this shows the increasing importance of sustainability in the oil industry

worldwide and in the Philippines. It also provides a basis for comparing how companies like Shell and Petron adopt different approaches to environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices.

METHODOLOGY

This research employs a comparative analysis design. It systematically compares the sustainability initiatives of Shell Pilipinas Corporation and Petron Corporation in 2023 based on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG). The research focuses on ESG indicator analysis and data visualization to objectively present and interpret the sustainability performance of Shell and Petron in 2023. The data focused on three ESG categories: Environmental (emissions, renewable energy, net-zero goals), Social (community investments, foundation programs), and Governance (ESG committees, reporting standards).

ESG Framework

The research follows the ESG model, which focuses on environmental impact (GHG emissions and renewable energy integration), social responsibility (financial and operational community engagement), and governance (corporate sustainability oversight and adherence to reporting standards). ESG is a structured approach for evaluating how organizations handle sustainability and ethical concerns.

Comparative Analysis

The primary method used in this research is comparative analysis. Shell and Petron's performance was analyzed using ESG indicators to evaluate the effectiveness of their initiatives. The analysis included side-by-side comparisons of quantitative figures, reported targets and goals, qualitative aspects of sustainability programs, governance structures, and the reporting standards adopted.

Data Visualization

Bar charts and tables are used in this research to effectively present and interpret the datasets. Bar charts, created using Power BI, compare the number of solar-powered sites and

community investments. Tables are employed to organize and summarize data, highlighting key differences and similarities in the companies' ESG strategies.

This research focuses solely on Shell Pilipinas' and Petron Corporation's 2023 ESG disclosures. The analysis is based on the 2023 sustainability reports, as Petron has not yet released its 2024 report. The study does not cover data before 2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data from the 2023 sustainability reports of Shell Pilipinas Corporation and Petron Corporation were analyzed to evaluate the

effectiveness of their Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) initiatives. Additionally, the financial reports of Shell and Petron for 2023 were also examined to determine the relationship between their sustainability initiatives and earnings growth.

Table 1 presents a comparative overview of key Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) indicators reported by Petron and Shell for 2023. The data show significant differences in their sustainability performance and strategic approaches.

Table 1. Comparative Overview of ESG Indicators for Petron and Shell Pilipinas (2023)

Category	Subcategory	Petron	Shell
Environmental	Emissions - Scope 1 GHG	3,964,260.97 MTCO ₂ e	837.1 tCO ₂ e
	Emissions - Scope 2 GHG	53,293.25 MT CO ₂ e	14,105.5 tCO ₂ e
	Percentage Change in Scope 2 GHG (2023 vs 2022)	Decreased by 18% vs 2022	Decreased by around 20% year on year
	Renewable Energy - Retail Sites with Solar Installations	At least 79 service stations	176 out of 200 mobility sites with solar panels
	Renewable Energy - Sites Running on 100% Renewable Energy	None reported as 100% renewable	3 sites: Batangas Import Terminal, SLEX Mamplasan, and NLEX Bulacan mobility sites.
	Net Zero Target	No specific net-zero target year is explicitly mentioned	Target aligned with Shell plc: Net-zero emissions energy business by 2050
Social	Social Impact - Total Community Investment	PHP 52,000,000	PHP 158,000,000
Governance	ESG Committee/Council	The ESG Council, led by the General Manager & CFO and including Senior Management, develops and implements the ESG strategy.	Board-level Sustainability Committee oversees social and sustainability initiatives, reviews content, and conducts materiality assessments via the VP committee.
	Sustainability Reporting Standards	Follows GRI Standards, Philippine SEC Guidelines, UN SDGs, and Philippine Development Plan. Adopts double materiality	Follows Philippine SEC Guidelines, GRI Standards, TCFD, and SASB.

Environmental

Table 1 shows a comparison of Net Zero Targets, GHG emissions (Scope 1 and 2), and

renewable energy initiatives of Shell Pilipinas and Petron Corporation in 2023. Shell aims for net-zero by 2050, aligned with Shell plc and the UN Paris Agreement, with a clear emissions reduction plan.

Petron commits to reducing its impact but has no set net-zero target year. Shell's Scope 1 emissions (837.1 tCO2e) are far lower than Petron's 3.96 million tCO2e due to operational scale and increased crude processing at Petron. Petron has doubled its GHG reductions since 2022, but Shell's 90% Scope 1 emission cut since 2016 and goal to cut Scope 1 and 2 by 50% by 2030 show a more aggressive approach. Hence, Shell appears more advanced in its emissions strategy, while Petron is gradually improving its environmental performance.

Figure 1. Comparison of Solar-Equipped Sites: Shell vs. Petron (2023)

Figure 1 compares solar installations by Shell and Petron in the Philippines. Both have made progress, but Shell's approach is more advanced. In 2023, Petron had solar panels at 79 service stations and solar-powered perimeter lighting at three terminals, mainly supplementing energy needs. Shell installed panels at 176 of 200 mobility sites and over 5,200 panels at terminals, with several sites fully powered by renewables. Shell also runs the world's first 100% geothermal-powered EV charger at the Neo Building in Bonifacio Global City. This shows that Shell is leading in using renewable energy and is more dedicated to using clean energy.

Social

Figure 2. Total Community Investment: Shell vs. Petron (2023)

Figure 2 compares the community investments made by Shell Pilipinas and Petron in 2023. Shell reported a significantly higher investment of PHP 158 million to support 18 programs through the Philippine Shell Foundation, Inc. (PSFI). On the other hand, Petron Foundation, Inc. (PFI) invested PHP 52 million in corporate social responsibility. Both companies recognize "Local Communities" as a material ESG topic and implement programs to address community needs. Shell's initiatives include STEM education, access to energy, and environmental awareness campaigns. Petron focuses on development programs and conducts impact assessments, with community involvement supported by a Multi-Partite Monitoring Team at its refinery. This comparison emphasizes Shell's larger scale of community engagement and funding in 2023.

Governance

Table 1 compares the governance and reporting practices of Shell and Petron. Petron's ESG Council, led by the GM & CFO with Senior Management, oversees ESG strategy and reporting using a double materiality approach. Shell has a Board-level Sustainability Committee managing social performance and stakeholder engagement, with materiality assessed by key executives. Both companies align with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Standards, including GRI 11: Oil and Gas Sector 2021 and GRI 1: Foundation 2021, and comply with the Philippine Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) reporting guidelines. Shell improves transparency by adopting the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) and the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB). Petron aligns its ESG topics with the Philippine Development Plan and UN SDGs. Both show strong governance, but Shell integrates more international ESG frameworks.

Table 2. Financial Performance of Petron vs Shell

Category	Petron	Shell
Net income	PHP 10.13 billion	PHP 1,182,902
Earnings growth (per unit of market cap)	0.1065%	Shell do not include information regarding the market capitalisation

Table 2 compares 2023 financials, showing Petron's net income rose to PHP 10.13 billion with positive earnings growth, while Shell's net income dropped to PHP 1.18 million, with no growth data due to missing market cap information.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The comparative analysis of Shell Pilipinas Corporation (SPC) and Petron Corporation's 2023 sustainability initiatives shows different approaches to Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices within the Philippines oil industry. Based on the 2023 ESG reports and financial performance of both companies, it is recommended that the Philippine oil industry continue to integrate ESG initiatives into their core business strategies.

The results indicate that Shell Pilipinas Corporation, despite economic challenges, reported a net income of PHP 1,182,902 in 2023. However, no information was provided regarding their market capitalization. In contrast, Petron Corporation shows stronger financial performance with a net income of PHP 10.13 billion and an earnings growth of 0.1065% per unit of market capitalization, while continuing efforts to reduce emissions and allocating over PHP 100 million to social development.

These findings substantiate existing study suggesting a positive relationship between ESG performance and corporate performance. Therefore, it is recommended that oil companies continue to invest in ESG initiatives not only for compliance but also as a business strategy that could promote operational efficiency and long-term profitability.

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